

IMPLEMENTATION OF LESSON STUDY BASED ON SAINTIFICATION IN LEARNING OF EARLY CHILDREN AGE

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Abstract

This study aimed to describe the implementation of scientific-based lesson study on early childhood learning. The type of this study was a case study and it involved 6 teachers of kindergarten Kemala Bhayangkari Batang district and was assisted by 2 people as resources from practitioners of early childhood education (PAUD). The object was the implementation of lesson study on early childhood learning through a scientific approach. Data were collected through observation, documentation, and interviews. The data were analyzed by descriptive analysis technique. The results showed; 1) lesson study can be carried out on early childhood learning and received positive response from PAUD teachers in Batang Hari district, 2) lesson study activities can improve teachers' ability in planning and implementing learning with scientific approach, and 3) the process of learning activities is better than the activities before the lesson study activity is carried out.

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1. Introduction

The success of an educational process can not be separated from the expertise of teachers as the spearhead of implementers in the field. As good as any learning program that is in the curriculum, it will not be of value if there are no highly competent professional teachers. Meanwhile, getting the figure of a professional teacher is not an easy matter, especially at the level of early childhood education. The previous studies showed that teaching will be more effective if the child's self-exploration is still supported by teacher guidance [Nayfield, 2011].

PAUD teachers need ongoing coaching to be able to understand their profession completely. Answering the need for sustained teacher-building efforts, a brilliant breakthrough called "lesson study" has been developed and popularized in Japan since the 1960s. At PAUD level, lesson study is still very rare, because in the world of early childhood, it does not recognize any particular subjects. Learning that can be used as research base is Science learning. In general, it can be said that early childhood learning is science-based learning because science in early childhood is a learning through natural process that is carried out constantly and introduced from an early age [Wickstrom, 2002]

This study explored how a scientific-based lesson study can be applied in early childhood educational institutions in Batanghari District. This can be said to be unprecedented, since teachers usually get direct coaching from district agencies or professional organizations through training or tiered training.

2. Literature Reviews

The National Association for the Education of Young Children (NAECY) in Brewer defines early childhood as a child in the age range 0-8 years [Brewer, 2007]. The regulation of minister of education and culture in Indonesian Republic number 146 in 2014 on Curriculum 13 PAUD in annex IV, stated that the concept of early childhood learning is centered on children. It is used as a scientific approach that includes a series of processes of observing, asking, gathering information, reasoning and communicating. The whole process is carried out by using all the senses as well as various sources and learning media.

Furthermore, Styler and Hiebert [1999] mentioned that lesson study is a collaborative process on a group of teachers when identifying learning problems, designing a learning scenario (which includes searching for books and articles on topics to be taught); educating learners according to the scenario (one teacher does another chase while others are watching), evaluating and revising the learning scenario, revising the revised learning scenario, re-evaluating the learning and sharing the results with other teachers (disseminate it). Sukirman [2006] also said the lesson study stage is divided into three stages, the those stages can be seen from the chart below:

Figure 1. Stages of Lesson Study

3. Method

This study was a qualitative descriptive method with a case study approach, and it was used to describe facts, data, or research object. Data were taken in Kemala Bhayangkari Kindergarten of Batang Hari District. Six teachers and 2 resource persons from PAUD practitioners were involved as the participants in this study. The focus of this study was in the implementation of scientific-based lesson study on early childhood learning. This study was completed with 2 cycles and each cycle consists of 3 stages of *plan*, *do* and *see*.

4. Result and Discussion

This study began by designing a scientific learning program plan which is a lesson study to be implemented to collaborative learners, where at this stage, all participants and academics involved will also observe the lesson plan. Furthermore, observation focused on the implementation of learning by scientific approach by teacher model based on the planning that has been made collaboratively, then observed by other teachers involving academics who acted as observers. The observers held observation sheets then followed by observations at the stage of reflecting the observation of the learning process to be evaluated in the discussion forum in order to know the advantages and disadvantages to be improved in the next learning. This activity was continued through 2 cycles, so that the process of learning activities become better than the previous learning activities.

The result of interview on teacher's impression when becoming teacher model is initially the teacher feel nervous because not accustomed to teach in condition observed by his colleague. However, the model teacher was also pleased with the inputs received from the observer. Similarly, other teachers feel happy to be observers, because teachers can observe the way other teachers who become models in dealing with students. So that teachers understand and get direct experience of early childhood learning process with scientific approach.

2. Conclusions and Recommendations

A scientific-based lesson study can be applied to early childhood learning, it is necessary as a more targeted solution/ alternative to teacher problems in the field. There are many differences with the existing PAUD training. Proven by 2 times of lesson study cycle that made significant changes in carrying out the learning process activities in early childhood. Especially on the ability of teachers in planning and implementing learning with a scientific approach. That by understanding how the implementation procedure of lesson study at PAUD level can improve the competence of pedagogy and professional competence of PAUD teachers. Hopefully, this will be a scientific reference for others especially for PAUD teachers to follow this step.

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